

THE PRESENCE OF INFORMATION SECURITY IN THE POLISH AND CZECH NATIONAL CORE CURRICULA

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Abstract

The topic of information security today already holds significant importance, and its relevance is expected to grow even further due to the increasing expansion of digitalization. Therefore, students need to learn about online threats within the education framework and understand how to protect themselves against them. Our current research examines the Czech Republic and Poland National Core Curricula. We are comparing the number of IT lessons, and exploring how information security is represented in the two countries' National Core Curricula.

Keywords

Information security, National Core Curriculum, Education, Poland, Czech Republic

1 Introduction

The rapid development of digital technology has fundamentally transformed our daily lives, especially among younger generations. The internet has become an integral part of students' daily lives, offering entertainment and communication opportunities and playing a significant role in education and learning. According to the latest research, students primarily use the online space to watch videos, listen to music, communicate with family and friends, visit social media sites, play online games, complete school assignments, browse shopping, and search for news. This diverse range of uses highlights the importance of learning and applying the basics of information security from an early age (EU Kids Online, 2020). As the time spent in the digital space increases, it becomes increasingly important for students to use online tools consciously, safely, and responsibly (Michalski & Gądek-Hawlena, 2022).

Students must know basic internet security rules, such as using secure passwords. A secure password is strong, unique, and regularly updated, serving as the foundation for protecting accounts. Additionally, special attention should be given to using two-factor authentication (2FA), which provides an additional layer of security. With 2FA, the user must provide a second identifier in addition to the password, such as a code received via SMS or generated by an authenticator app. This significantly reduces the risk of account breaches (Pásztor, 2024).

Furthermore, students need to know which websites provide credible and reliable information. They must approach online content critically and be able to distinguish credible sources from fake news or misleading information. They must also be aware not to open emails

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from unknown sources, which often contain malicious links or attachments that compromise account security (Zhang & A. Ghorbani, 2020).

The safe use of the online space helps students navigate the internet confidently while protecting their data and avoiding cyber threats. Acquiring proper internet security knowledge at a young age lays the foundation for responsible digital presence, which has become almost indispensable in our lives (Tomczyk & Kopecký, 2016).

Nowadays, digitalization and IT are playing an increasingly important role in education. The use of technologies like cloud computing, online assessments, and virtual collaboration tools is making education more flexible and responsive to individuals' needs. learners (Dancsa, Štempeľová, Takáč, & Annuš, 2023).

Moreover, digital tools support the development of key competencies that are essential for future careers. As technology continues to evolve, students must develop digital literacy skills that will help them navigate and adapt to new tools and platforms (Takáč, Kanta, & Takáčová, 2023).

2 Research Methodology

In the research, we applied a document analysis method, examining the official state-issued National Core Curricula of Poland and the Czech Republic. The analysis aims to explore and compare the presence, content, and emphasis of information security in the IT National Core Curricula of the two countries and examine the number of IT lessons prescribed for each grade level. Our research examines the IT National Core Curricula of the V4 countries through pairwise comparisons. We seek to determine the level of detail in which information security appears in each country's state-issued National Core Curricula.

3 Research Limitations

During the research, it was necessary to consider the different structures of the two compared educational systems, which posed limitations in interpreting the results. Primary school in the Czech Republic lasts 9 years, while in Poland, it lasts 8 years. The division of lower and upper primary school grades also differs between the two countries. The Czech Republic's lower primary level includes grades 1–5, while the upper primary level covers grades 6–9. The lower primary level in Poland consists of grades 1–3, and the upper primary level includes grades 4–8.

Another limitation of the research is that in Poland, the state-issued National Core Curriculum for lower primary education does not specify a concrete number of IT lessons nor provides detailed guidelines for them.

4 IT lesson hours in the Czech Republic and Poland

Information security is taught within the framework of the IT subject in both countries. Both countries have centrally defined, state-developed National Core Curricula that schools must follow. Based on these central regulations, individual institutions must develop their school-level Core Curriculum, ensuring that the educational content aligns with state guidelines and requirements (Poland, 2024), (Czechia, 2024).

Tab. 5: IT Lesson Hours in the Czech Republic and Poland

		Czech Republic	Poland
primary school	lower primary school*	2 hours	this changes***
	upper primary school**	4 hours	5 hours
Grammar school		4 hours	3 hours

Source: (Rámcový vzdělávací program pro základní vzdělávání, 2023), (Rámcový vzdělávací program pro gymnázia, 2007), (Strona główna Sejmu Rzeczpospolitej Polskiej, 2024)

* In the Czech Republic, grades 1–5; in Poland, grades 1–3.

** In the Czech Republic, grades 6–9; in Poland, grades 4–8.

*** The teacher determines the specific number of IT lessons, taking into account the students' abilities; however, the Core Curriculum mandates that IT lessons must be included at this educational level.

5 The presence of information security in the Polish National Core Curriculum for IT lessons

The state-issued National Core Curriculum for IT consists of the following three main parts at both primary and grammar school levels:

- learning objectives,
- educational content,
- implementation conditions and methods.

These elements collectively define the framework for IT education, ensuring a comprehensive and structured approach to teaching the subject.

The learning objectives of the National Core Curriculum are categorized into five key areas. First, it emphasizes the importance of understanding, analyzing, and solving problems, fostering critical thinking and logical reasoning skills. Additionally, programming and problem-solving using computers and other digital devices play a crucial role, encouraging students to develop computational thinking. The curriculum also focuses on effectively using computers, digital devices, and computer networks, equipping students with essential technological skills. Furthermore, it aims to enhance social competence, highlighting the importance of collaboration and communication in the digital world. Lastly, compliance with laws and safety regulations is fundamental, ensuring that students understand ethical considerations and cybersecurity principles. These components collectively provide a well-rounded IT education, preparing students for the challenges of the digital age.

Information security is addressed by complying with laws and safety regulations.

Primary school lower grades (grades 1–3): The National Core Curriculum at this level does not include guidelines for the IT subject.

Primary school upper grades (grades 4–8): The National Core Curriculum uniformly defines the learning objectives for upper primary school, while the educational content is divided into two parts: grades 4–6 and grades 7–8.

Learning objectives (grades 4–8): For the safety of oneself and others, it is essential to adhere to information privacy and data protection, respect intellectual property rights, communication etiquette, and social cooperation norms, as well as assess and consider technology-related risks for the safety of oneself and others (Ministra, 2024).

Educational content:

In grades 4–6, the student:

- Uses technology according to accepted principles and regulations, adhering to occupational safety requirements.
- Respects data protection, information privacy, and intellectual property rights.
- Lists the risks associated with widespread access to technology and information and explains methods to protect against them.

In grades 7–8, the student:

- Demonstrates ethical issues related to the use of computers and computer networks, such as security, digital identity, privacy protection, intellectual property, equal access to information, and information sharing.
- Acts ethically in handling information.
- Distinguishes between different types of licenses for software and online Resources (Ministra, 2024).

Grammar school level:

Learning objectives:

- Compliance with laws and safety regulations.
- Respect for information privacy, data protection, intellectual property rights, communication etiquette, and social norms.
- Assessment and consideration of technology-related risks to ensure one's safety and that of others.

Educational content - the student:

1. Adheres to the principles of netiquette and the following regulations when accessing information: personal data protection, information security, copyright laws, and intellectual property protection. The student is aware of the potential consequences of violating these rules.
2. Respects the applicable laws and ethical standards regarding using and distributing computer software, third-party and self-developed applications, and electronic documents.
3. Apply best practices to protect sensitive information (e.g., passwords, and PIN codes), ensure data and operating system security, and explain the role of information encryption.
4. Explains the harm caused by online piracy activities, affecting individuals, selected institutions, and society.

The student meets the basic requirements and additionally:

- Explains the role of authentication techniques, cryptography, and electronic signatures in protecting information and accessing information.
- Discusses the importance of encryption and electronic signature algorithms (Ministra edukacji, 2024).

6 The presence of information security in the Czech National Core Curriculum for IT lessons

From the National Core Curriculum, we can learn that the topic of information security does not explicitly appear at either the primary or grammar school level.

In the primary school curriculum, the various components are categorized into three groups:

- Expected outcomes,
- The minimum recommended level of outcomes within the framework of supporting measures,
- Educational content.

In the lower primary school level, digital technology highlights the concept of safety, with rules for safe use of digital devices, user accounts, and passwords mentioned. However, the National Core Curriculum does not reference information security in the expected outcomes or the minimum recommended level of outcomes within the framework of supporting measures.

In the upper primary school level of the National Core Curriculum, under the topic of digital technology, the following is written about safety:

- Expected outcomes: The student can manage their activities to minimize the risk of data loss or misuse, describe the operation of security solutions, and discuss their limitations.
- Minimum recommended level of expected outcomes: The student can manage their activities to reduce the risk of data loss and misuse.
- Educational content:
Computer networks: Principles of cloud applications; methods for securing data access, roles, and access rights.
Security: Attacks – goals and methods of attackers, dangerous applications and systems; security of digital devices and data – updates, antivirus software, firewalls, secure handling of passwords and password managers, two-factor authentication, data and communication encryption, backups, and archiving (MŠMT, 2023).

Grammar school level:

At the grammar school level, within the National Core Curriculum, information security also appears as part of the IT subject. In digital technology, the expected outcomes state that the student effectively organizes and protects data from damage or misuse. The curriculum section, under the topic of data maintenance and protection, covers compression, antivirus protection, firewalls, and data backup, regarding source and information searching, communication, the expected outcomes state that the student creatively assesses the timeliness, relevance, and credibility of information sources and information. In the curriculum guidance related to this topic, within the subject of information ethics and legislation, it addresses copyright and personal data protection (Ministerstvo školství, mládeže a tělovýchovy, 2007).

7 Conclusion

In Poland, the lower primary level covers only grades 1–3, and the National Core Curriculum does not provide detailed guidance on the content of the IT subject, merely stating that IT must be included. In the Czech Republic, the curriculum specifies that at the lower primary level, which includes grades 1–5, there must be a minimum of two IT lessons.

Both countries' curricula address information security in roughly similar detail at the upper primary level. In the Czech Republic, this level includes grades 6–9, where students have 4 IT lessons. In Poland, this level covers grades 4–8, where students are required to have 5 IT lessons.

The Czech National Core Curriculum prescribes 4 IT lessons at the grammar school level, while the Polish curriculum requires three lessons.

It is difficult to compare the extent to which information security is represented at different educational levels based on the National Core Curriculum, as the educational levels are structured differently in both countries. At the lower primary level, the Polish curriculum merely states that there must be IT lessons. The National Core Curriculum references user accounts and passwords in the Czech Republic.

At the upper primary level, the National Core Curriculum in the Czech Republic and Poland includes information security, but to varying extents. In the Czech Republic, the curriculum covers secure password management, password managers, two-factor authentication, data backups, and the importance of firewalls. In contrast, the Polish curriculum addresses information privacy, the protection of digital identity, and the ethical handling of information. At this level, the Czech National Core Curriculum more specifically mentions individual concepts related to information security.

At the grammar school level in Poland, students learn to adhere to the principles of netiquette, protect personal data, respect copyright laws, and comply with legislation regarding intellectual property. For example, they learn about PIN codes and passwords. Students understand the societal harm caused by piracy activities. In the Czech Republic, the curriculum addresses the credibility of information. It covers antivirus protection, firewalls, data backups, and copyright and personal data protection.

In summary, students in Poland and the Czech Republic are introduced to user accounts and passwords as early as the lower primary level. In the Czech Republic, this is mandated by the National Core Curriculum, whereas in Poland, it depends on the teacher's discretion regarding what they consider important. In Poland, if a teacher does not prioritize information security at the lower primary school level, students at this stage do not acquire adequate knowledge in this area. As a result, they are exposed to increased risks in the digital space, lacking the fundamental skills needed to protect themselves from online threats. This makes them more vulnerable to cyberattacks, such as account breaches and unauthorized access to their online profiles. Without early education on cybersecurity principles, students may develop unsafe online habits, making them more susceptible to phishing attempts, identity theft, and other forms of digital exploitation.

More emphasis should be placed on teaching information security in the state-issued school National Core Curricula of both countries. Students should be introduced to the basics of information security as early as the first grade of primary school, as they register on online platforms at an increasingly younger age. They should know how to create strong passwords, where and how to store them securely, and what two-factor authentication is. Special attention should also be given to which personal information should not be shared on social media. The national Core Curriculum should incorporate more interactive, real-life examples and practical

exercises for more effective learning. If policymakers implemented these recommendations, students could gain a deeper understanding of information security principles at an earlier stage.

If students are introduced to information security principles later than when they start using various online platforms, they are at increased risk in the digital space. The lack of basic knowledge makes them more likely to fall victim to cyberattacks, phishing, and other online abuses.

8 Resources

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